

RUBBER PAD FORMING OF GLARE CRUCIFORM USING NUMERICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL ANALYSIS

R. Subbaramaiah^{1,2*}, S. H. Lim^{1,2}, B. G. Prusty¹, G. Pearce¹, D. Kelly¹, R. Thomson^{2,3}

¹ University of New South Wales, Sydney, Australia, ² Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures, Fishermans Bend, Australia, ³ Advanced Composite Structures Australia Pty Ltd, Port Melbourne, Australia

*Corresponding author: ravishankar.subbaramaiah@unsw.edu.au

Keywords: *Rubber pad forming, Fibre Metal Laminate, GLARE,*

1 Introduction

Fibre Metal Laminates (FMLs) have been increasingly applied to reinforce aluminium applications such as helicopter subfloors due to their compatibility with aluminium [1]. Thus, the Cooperative Research Centre for Advanced Composite Structures (CRC-ACS) is conducting research on retrofitting FMLs to enhance the crashworthiness of aged metallic airframes [2]. One of the nominal examples of FMLs is GLARE (GLASS REINFORCED aluminium) which comes readily available as pre-cured flat sheets. The forming of GLARE into a more complex structure, however, is limited by the brittleness of the composite laminate sandwiched in between thin metallic layers [3]. This results in extensive research [4-6] dedicated to forming process for GLARE without inducing internal damage/failures.

Edwardson et al. [4] conducted laser forming and found cracks and buckling in metal produced by uncontrolled localised heating. The generated heat also induced delamination between layers. The drawing behaviour of metal composite sandwich was studied by Gresham et al. [5], and severe wrinkling was noted during drawing operations. Mosse et al. [6] proposed preheating before forming and holding the laminate between dies until polymer solidification and the process minimised shape error and delamination. This process, however, required precise temperature conditions and forming rate and might affect the characteristics that exist in FML sheets. Flexible rubber pad forming [7] is shown to be a good manufacturing process well suited to FMLs.

In this paper the formability of GLARE using rubber pad forming is investigated to develop a retrofitable hat-shaped energy absorbing component. The experimental setup for rubber

pad forming is first constructed based on the Guerin method. Explicit finite element analysis is then developed to predict the formability of these retrofit structures. The modelling methodology is verified and improved with aluminium sheet and the constructed experimental setup. The numerical and experimental analyses are then conducted for hat-shaped GLARE forming process.

2 FMLs and Rubber Pad Forming

FMLs consist of alternate thin layers of metal and fibre reinforced epoxy, bonded together using an adhesive. FMLs are being used for various applications in the aerospace industry due to their superior performance. There are two main manufacturing techniques associated with FML; (a) using layup technology to arrange layers of metal and prepreg to the required shape prior to curing and (b) to adopt sheet metal forming technique to form the FML to required shape after curing.

2.1 GLARE

GLARE is currently being investigated as a material for enhancing crashworthiness, by designing suitable retrofitable cruciform structures. As shown in Fig. 1, GLARE comprises alternating layers 2024-aluminium and S2-Glass fibre epoxy composite, bonded together using FM-94 epoxy adhesive.

Fig. 1. Typical GLARE with 3/2 layup [1].

Table 1 lists the various grades and sub-grades of GLARE that are defined by types and

thicknesses of aluminium and the fibre orientation of each glass fibre epoxy composite prepreg layers. GLARE-2A sheets were selected to form the hat-shaped component as the fibres are parallel to the bend line allowing the formation of sharper bend radii. The selected aluminium thickness is 0.4mm and the thickness of GLARE 2A with 2/1 layup is 1.2mm.

Table 1. Available grades of GLARE [1].

Grade	Sub-grade	Metal sheet thickness [mm] and alloy	Prepreg orientation in each layer
Glare 1		0.3 – 0.4 7475-T761	0/0
Glare 2	2A	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	0/0
	2B	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	90/90
Glare 3		0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	0/90
Glare 4	4A	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	0/90/0
	4B	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	90/0/90
Glare 5		0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	0/90/90/0
Glare 6	6A	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	+45/-45
	6B	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	-45/+45
Glare 7	7A	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	0/+45/-45/0
	7B	0.2 – 0.5 2024-T3	90/-45/+45/90

2.2 Rubber Pad Forming Guerin Method

Rubber pad forming (RPF) is a preferred forming process to maintain the surface finish quality of the sheets. It achieves minimal thickness variation, reduces alignment and mismatch problems and is cost effective. Hence RPF best suits for GLARE to maintain the integrity of all layers and along the bonded surfaces. Fig. 2 illustrates the RPF Guerin methodology. RPF uses a flexible rubber die/tool to form the sheet/blank over a hard rigid die.

Fig. 2. Rubber pad sizing.

In the Guerin method, the flexible die has to be at least three times thicker than the height of

the formed specimen X and at least two times wider than the width of the specimen Y.

3 Rubber Pad Forming of FMLs

3.1 Rubber Pad Forming Setup

Fig. 3 shows the experimental setup that adopts the Guerin method to form sheets into hat-shaped component. A uniaxial high performance Instron machine that can operate up to 250kN with a maximum stroke of 130mm covered the required forming force and tool travel. The applied forming force and tool travel data was recorded by the data acquisition system integrated with the Instron machine.

Fig. 3. Rubber pad forming setup.

The rubber pad forming (RPF) setup was initially established by employing three polyurethane pads of Shore A hardness of 70 as the flexible die. A hardened steel male die shown in Fig. 4 was used in this process to manufacture the required hat/trapezoidal profiles. The dimensions of the rigid die for hat profile are 25mm height and 90mm width. Thus, three polyurethane pads of thickness 10mm, 25mm and 40mm were used to obtain the required height 75mm, as previously described in Section 2.2.

Fig. 4. Rigid die made of hardened steel.

The pads were cut to size 250mm x 250mm and were stacked on the platform/bed of the Instron machine to cover the required width. The flat sheet was held on to the die with two tap screws. As shown in Fig. 5, the rigid die and the held sheet was placed on top of the

flexible die. The actuator head of the Instron machine was lowered and a circular disc was used to push the rigid die into the flexible die to form the hat/trapezoidal structures.

Fig. 5. RPF setup with sheet/blank, rigid and flexible die.

3.2 Explicit FEA Model Description

The explicit finite element analysis tool LS-DYNA [8] was used to simulate and predict the formability of GLARE. The hybrid material with aluminium 2024-T3 and E-Glass/Epoxy was modelled using a layered shell methodology. The top and bottom layers were aluminium of thickness 0.4 mm and the sandwiched Glass/Epoxy layer between the aluminium had a thickness of 0.25 mm. The element size was 1mm perpendicular to bend line and 3mm parallel to bend line.

The layers of GLARE were meshed with quad shell elements with Belytschko-Tsay element formulation elements. The elements used one in-plane integration point and a minimum of three integration points through the thickness to capture the plastic hinge formation. Hourglass controls were used to inhibit the nonphysical modes of deformation. Flanagan-Belytschko stiffness form was used with default hourglass coefficients (default 0.15). Stability can be increased by invoking bulk viscosity of shell element formulation. The aluminium layer was modelled with a Johnson Cook material model which included damage and strain-rate sensitive plasticity. Thermal effects were not taken into account. The material properties for aluminium are presented in

Table 2 while the material properties of E-Glass/Epoxy are presented in Table 3.

Table 2. Material properties of aluminium 2024-T3, 6061-T6 [9] .

Aluminium type	2024-T3	6061-T6
A_1 (MPa)	369	324
B_1 (MPa)	684	114
N	0.73	0.42
C	0.0083	0.002
D_1	0.13	-0.77
D_2	0.13	1.45
D_3	-1.5	-0.47
D_4	0.011	0
σ_{ult} (MPa)	483	310

Table 3. Material properties of E-Glass/Epoxy [10].

Property	Description	Glass
ρ (g/cm ³)	Density	1.80
E_{1f} (GPa)	Longitudinal modulus (fibre direction)	30.9
E_{2f} (GPa)	Transverse modulus (perpendicular to fibre)	8.3
G_{12} (GPa)	In-plane shear modulus	2.8
ν_{12}	Minor Poisson's ratio	0.0866
σ_{1t} (MPa)	Longitudinal tensile strength (fibre direction)	798
σ_{1c} (MPa)	Longitudinal compressive strength (fibre direction)	480
σ_{2t} (MPa)	Transverse tensile strength (perpendicular to fibre)	40
σ_{2c} (MPa)	Transverse compressive strength (perpendicular to fibre)	140
τ_{12} (MPa)	In-plane shear strength	70
DFAILT	Maximum strain for fibre tension	2.3 %
DFAILC	Maximum strain for fibre compression	1.4 %

The fibres in the composite layer were along the rolling direction so that the bend lines were parallel to the fibre orientation. E-Glass/Epoxy was modelled using an enhanced composite damage model [8] in LS-DYNA. A modified version of the Hashin failure criterion, namely Chang-Chang, was applied in the damage model. Here tensile and compressive fibre and matrix failure were separately considered. After failure is encountered, the stiffness of the elements is reduced gradually to near zero before the element is completely removed after a pre-defined maximum strain is reached. In addition the layer in the element is completely removed after the maximum tensile or

compressive strain in the fibre direction is reached [8]. The failure equations using Chang-Chang criterion utilised four indicator functions corresponding to the four failure modes.

A graphical representation of composite material models available in LS-DYNA is shown in Fig. 6 for comparison. Additional measures were taken to delete elements which were highly distorted. The polyurethane pads which were used as a flexible die were modelled with a Mooney-Rivlin material model [12]. The coefficients A and B of the material model are given in the Table 4. The element size for the rubber model was kept identical to that of the formed specimen for regions in the vicinity of the sheet/blank while a gradually increasing mesh size was used for the region away from the specimen. The polyurethane pads were meshed with 1 point nodal pressure tetrahedron solid elements for bulk forming. Default hourglass coefficients were used. Negative volumes in highly distorted elements occurred, especially for the solid elements of flexible die, and the offending elements were deleted so that the calculation could continue.

Fig. 6. Composite material models in LS-DYNA (MAT58) [11].

Table 4. Polyurethane material properties for MAT27 [12].

Poly urethane	A	B	Poisson Ratio	Density (kg/mm ³)
Shore A 70	0.73	0.18	0.499	2.00E-06
	6	4		

Other components, such as the circular disc and die were all modelled as rigid. Contacts are defined to represent the interaction between the two materials and avoid interpenetration as follows:

Contact Automatic Surface to Surface Tie (CASST) was used to represent the bond between composite and aluminium layers.

After failure, this contact option behaved as a surface-to-surface contact. The failure criterion has normal failure stress and shear failure stress governed by [8]

$$\left(\frac{|\sigma_n|}{NFLS}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{|\sigma_s|}{SFLS}\right)^2 \geq 1. \quad (1)$$

A general contact was defined to represent contacting surface between rigid die, sheet/blank, die, frame, polyurethane pad and circular disc. The locating screws that ensured the sheet was in place were defined by a tied contact at nodes in the region of these screws.

The frame was constrained in all degrees of freedom. The die and circular disc were constrained to move only in the vertical direction and a prescribed motion was defined on the disc to define the stroke/travel. The lower surface of the polyurethane pad was constrained. The forming force for a given die travel was extracted. Other direct outputs like material thinning, overall stress and deformation plots were also extracted. The springback angle can be estimated in post-processing by measuring the distance between reference nodes. Failures in the individual layers of the hybrid component or bond failure between the aluminium and composite were reported.

3.3 Validation of Modelling Methodology

The developed numerical model was validated by comparing the springback angle determined from an analytical model [13] that derives the springback factor K_s . Using bend radii R , bend angle α , Young modulus E , thickness of sheet T and yield strength YS ; the springback factor K_s can be found approximately from:

$$K_s = \frac{\alpha_i}{\alpha_f} = \frac{R_i}{R_f} \\ = 4 \left(\frac{R_i YS}{E T}\right)^3 - 3 \left(\frac{R_i YS}{E T}\right) + 1 \quad (2)$$

to estimate the springback factor in terms of R_i and R_f , where i and f are before and after effect of springback. A springback factor of K_s equal to 1 means no springback. In this comparison, aluminium grade 6061-T6 sheets of 0.5mm and 1.27mm were used, where the material properties are listed in

Table 2. The evaluated bend radius is located at the bottom end of the hat shaped component, which was R3 as shown in Fig. 4. The springback angle estimated by FEA and analytical model for the aluminium sheets are shown below in Table 5. The differences of springback angle between the analytical model and explicit FEA are 0.21° for 0.5mm and 0.22° for 1.27mm. It is conclusive that the FEA model predicts the springback consistently for the various thickness of aluminium 6061-T6 sheets.

Table 5. Comparison of springback angle.

Aluminium 6061-T6 Thickness (mm)	Springback angle(°)	
	Analytical model	Explicit FEA
0.5	3.99	4.2
1.27	2.5	2.72

4 Results

The modelling methodology was employed to calibrate the experimental RPF setup in Section 3.1 such that the GLARE formation can be completed well within the maximum limits of forming force and tool travel. The calibrated setup was then utilised for GLARE formation and the formed GLARE was analysed numerically and experimentally.

4.1 Calibration of Experimental RPF Setup

Aluminium grade 6061-T6 sheets of thickness 0.5mm were also used to calibrate the experimental RPF setup. Two different investigations were conducted using the modelling methodology, where the first examined the flexible die behaviour during RPF and the resultant forming force. The second study was conducted to analyse the formed aluminium sheets. In the FEA model, the tool travel was set to be 34mm that covers the depth of the hat profile.

4.1.1 Investigation of Flexible Die Behaviour during RPF

The flexible die behaviour was investigated using two cases, where one was based on the experimental RPF setup while the other was the setup with the addition of a steel frame to confine or restrict the movement of flexible die to the direction transverse to the tool travel. The flexible die was modelled as three unbonded layers with the same thicknesses and stacking orientation given in Fig. 5 and Section 3.1. The steel frame was modelled as

rigid. Fig. 7 shows the flexible die behaviour in RPF, where (a) and (b) are the pre and post RPF when the flexible die was not confined while (c) and (d) are the pre and post RPF when the flexible die was confined by the steel frame. In the comparison between the two cases, addition of the steel frame to the RPF setup reduced the excess space due to unbonded layers of flexible die and thus provided a higher force concentration on the bend radii at the same tool travel. The addition of a steel frame would affect the forming force. The forming force based on these cases was extracted and was shown in Fig. 8. A lower forming force was required when the steel frame was incorporated as compared to RPF without the steel frame.

Fig. 7. Graphical interpretation of RPF without frame [(a) pre and (b) post] and with frame [(c) pre and (d) post].

Fig. 8. Forming force with and without steel frame.

Experiments were then conducted to confirm the findings from this investigation. A steel frame with internal area of 250mm x 250mm and thickness of 10mm was constructed and adopted to the experimental setup. When the steel frame was not utilised, a forming force of 230kN and 125mm tool travel were required for aluminium sheets to be formed and the formed aluminium sheets deviated from the required profile as there was significant

springback. Meanwhile, a lower forming force of 80kN was required when the steel frame was used in the experimental setup. Similarly, the required tool travel was also reduced to roughly 34mm.

4.1.2 Analysis of Formed Aluminium Sheets

The formed aluminium sheets in this analysis were based on the RPF setup with the steel frame. As shown in Fig. 9, it was seen in the analysis that the flexible die was not able to reach to bend radii along the web of the hat profiles. Hence it was required to make sure that the rubber pad could compress into these edges effectively. Two rubber pad wedges were cut as per the die profile, as depicted in Fig. 10, to ensure it would compress along the hat profile webs. These additional pads were glued to the underlying layers of flexible die. Experiments were also conducted to investigate the performance of the rubber pad wedges. Fig. 11 shows the formed aluminium sheets using the RPF setup with and without the rubber pad wedges. The springback angle of the sheet formed without the rubber pad wedges is greater than the sheet formed with the rubber pad wedges.

Fig. 9. Flexible die unable to form along tight bend radii.

Fig. 10. Additional pads provided to match rigid die profile.

Fig. 11. Formed aluminium sheets with and without rubber pad wedges

Thus, the resultant springback from the calibrated experimental RPF setup was primarily due the constituting material and because the rigid die was manufactured to dimensions of the hat profile without any springback allowance.

4.1.3 Investigation of Flexible Die Layers in Numerical Model

The Guerin method was usually applied with one layer of flexible die. Thus, the investigation of the unbonded flexible die layers was revisited using the numerical model to ensure that the flexible die behaviour was similar to one layer of flexible die. The flexible die was modelled in two different representations, which are the unbonded layers and one single layer. Fig. 12 shows the comparisons, which indicated that the model with unbonded layers provided slightly higher forming force at the beginning of tool travel. This is possibly due to additional force required to cover the excess space from the unbonded condition. The movement flexibility of the unbonded layers also allow additional volume concentrated at the bend radii from the beginning and resulted in less forming force required at the end of tool travel. At tool travel of 34mm, however, the same amount of forming force is required to form the sheet.

Fig. 12. Forming force comparison for single and three layers of flexible die.

The difference between bonded and unbonded condition is further illustrated in Fig. 13. The

advantage of using three layers is that they could be reused for other profiles and the top thin layer can be replaced after significant wear.

Fig. 13. Graphical interpretation of RPF with one [(a) pre and (b) post] or three [(c) pre and (d) post] layers of flexible die.

4.2 FE and Experiment Analysis in GLARE Formation using RPF

The GLARE formation using the calibrated RPF was first conducted based on the dimensions and the corresponding force given in Table 6 prior to GLARE formation of the full size component of 120mm x 98mm. The minimal force was based on numerical analysis to compress the flexible die completely over the rigid die along all bend radii while forming GLARE 2A. This exercise was required to investigate failure on the formed specimen and also to determine the required forming force to form the full size component.

Table 6. Test matrix for GLARE formation.

GLARE 2A	Forming force (kN)
25mm x 98mm	80
25mm x 98mm	123
25mm x 98mm	205

Optical microscope images are shown in Table 7 for the three GLARE specimen formed with different forming forces. The images correspond to the bend locations i.e. top and bottom. There was no visible damage in the metallic or composite layers. Thus, analysis of the experimental results indicated that, forming forces higher than 80kN had no or minimal change in the form of the profiles. The failure modes of GLARE specimen during forming listed in Table 8 was also not visible for all the different forming forces.

Table 7. Images extracted from optical microscope after RPF.

Table 9 it can be seen that for different forming forces the thickness variation is minimal.

Table 8. General failure modes during forming for FMLs [14].

Failure mode	Location	Example
Cracked metal layer of a v-bend specimen	Outer Metal	
Matrix cracks	Matrix	
Fibres failed in compression (kinks)	Centre of bend line	
Fibre tension failure	Can initiate delamination	
Delamination Buckling	Compressive zone in forming	
Inter-laminar Shear	Centre line of maximum shear stress	
Edge delamination	Specimen Edge	

Rubber pad forming is highly beneficial as no wrinkling is seen due to uniform application of pressure as compared to other forming process. The thinning is also minimal and in

Table 9. Thickness at bend radii.

GLARE 2A	Average Thickness (mm)	
	Bottom Radii (R3mm)	Top Radii (R4.6mm)
80kN	1.105	1.078
123kN	1.084	1.089
205kN	1.096	1.070

Fig. 14 shows the y-deformation at die travel of 42mm, which indicates that the GLARE sheet along tight bend radii was fully formed. At 42mm, the corresponding forming force in this numerical analysis was 132kN of forming force. The die travel was adopted to the full GLARE component formation.

Fig. 14. Y-Deformation at die travel of 42mm.

Based on successful calibration of the rubber pad forming process for GLARE and results from numerical analysis, it is evident that the procedure can be used to form samples that can be used for realistic applications. The holes on the full size GLARE component for clamping were drilled with 2 fluted drills as twist drills can delaminate the FMLs. The RPF process was performed on GLARE sheet in tool travel of 41.8mm which resulted in forming force of 120kN. The formed specimen is shown in Fig. 15. The springback in GLARE 2A having 3/2 layup is measured to be 2.25° that is less than 0.5mm thick aluminium 6061-T6, which had a springback of 4.2°. Fig. 16 shows the differences of springback when the formed 0.5mm thick aluminium 6061-T6 was stacked on top of the formed GLARE 2A.

The forming force (kN) to tool travel (mm) is compared for the experimental and numerical analysis. From Fig. 17 we can see that the numerical model is able to predict the forming force and tool travel accurately as compared to the experimental setup. The modelling methodology adopted could be used to simulate and predict formability of FMLs like GLARE using the rubber pad forming process.

Fig. 15. GLARE hat profile formed using RPF.

Fig. 16. Springback in GLARE and 0.5mm Al sheet.

Fig. 17. Comparison of forming force estimated from explicit FEA and experiments.

The rubber pad is able to deform the specimen completely on to the die as in the sectioned view in Fig. 18, and there has been only 5-6% thinning as shown in plots extracted from Ls-Prepost in Fig. 19. The springback was measured to be less than 3° as shown in Fig. 20.

Fig. 18. Deformation at maximum die travel.

Fig. 19. Fringe level distribution that indicates thinning variations of the formed GLARE.

Fig. 20. Springback of 2.25° measured in LS-DYNA.

5 Summary

It is concluded that rubber pad forming is a feasible technique to form doubly curved trapezoidal energy absorbing GLARE components. Numerical analysis can accurately predict the complicated rubber pad forming process with high accuracy. Minimal thinning of less than 6% is observed in this process with no wrinkles. The forming force and tool travel estimated by numerical analysis shows good comparison with that estimated experimentally.

The methodology adopted to estimate the formability of fibre metal laminate like GLARE in the explicit finite element analysis is proven to be a fast, cost effective tool to design and develop the forming process. The finite element analysis methodology can easily be extended to design other GLARE components using the rubber pad forming technique.

Future work will be focused on forming the hat profile to dimension by accounting for springback effect.

References

- [1] A. Vlot and J. W. Gunnink "Fiber Metal Laminates: An Introduction". Dordrecht, Netherlands: Kluwer Academic Publishers., 2001.
- [2] R. Subbaramaiah, B. G. Prusty, G. M. Pearce, S. H. Lim, D. W. Kelly, R. S. Thomson "A Feasibility Study for Multi-Material Retrofittable Energy Absorbing Structure for Aged Helicopter Subfloor". *International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences (ICAS)*, Brisbane, Australia, 2012.
- [3] J. Sinke "Manufacturing of GLARE Parts and Structures". *Applied Composite Materials*, Vol. 10, pp. 293-305, 2003.
- [4] S. P. Edwardson, P. French, G. Dearden, K. G. Watkins, and W. J. Cantwell "Laser Forming of Fibre Metal Laminates". *Lasers in Eng.*, Vol. 15, pp. 233-255, 2005.
- [5] J. Gresham, W. Cantwell, M. J. Cardew-Hall, P. Compston, and S. Kalyanasundaram "Drawing behaviour of metal-composite sandwich structures". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 75, pp. 305-312, 2006.
- [6] L. Mosse, P. Compston, W. J. Cantwell, M. Cardew-Hall, and S. Kalyanasundaram "The effect of process temperature on the formability of polypropylene based fibre-metal laminates". *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 36, pp. 1158-1166, 2005.
- [7] S. Thiruvarudchelvan "Elastomers in metal forming: A review". *Journal of Materials Processing Tech.*, Vol. 39, pp. 55-82, 1993.
- [8] *LS-DYNA Keyword User's Manual, Version 971*, Vol. I and II, 2012.
- [9] T. P. Vo, Z. W. Guan, W. J. Cantwell, and G. K. Schleyer "Modelling of the low-impulse blast behaviour of fibre-metal laminates based on different aluminium alloys". *Composites Part B: Engineering*, Vol. 44, pp. 141-151, 2013.
- [10] H. Elhage, P. Mallick, and N. Zamani "A numerical study on the quasi-static axial crush characteristics of square aluminum-composite hybrid tubes". *Composite Structures*, Vol. 73, pp. 505-514, 2006.
- [11] R. Matheis "Numerical simulation of the crash behaviour of braided composites". *CFK-Valley Stade Convention*, 2011.
- [12] A. Del Prete, G. Papadia, B. Manisi, and A. Del Prete "Computer Aided Modelling of Rubber Pad Forming Process". *Key Engineering Materials*, Vol. 473, pp. 637-644.

- [13] V. Boljanovic "*Sheet Metal Forming Processes and Die Design*". Industrial Press, 2004.
- [14] T. W. De Jong "*Forming of laminates*". Delft: Delft University Press, 2004.

Acknowledgement

The GLARE sheets used in this study were provided by FMLC (Fibre Metal Laminates Centre of Competence). The authors would like to thank Peter J. Kortbeek and Cees van Hengel from FMLC for providing the GLARE samples.